

Data Management Plan (DMP) / Plan de Gestión de Datos (PGD)

Optimization of a tool to detect iso/hetero uniparental disomies in patients of the NAGEN Program

Original title: Optimización de una herramienta para la detección de iso/heterodisomías uniparentales en pacientes del Programa NAGEN.

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Background: This project proposes the validation of the bioinformatic tool UPDhmm, able to detect iso/hetero uniparental disomies, analysing the trios of the projects NAGEN1000 and NAGENpediatrics, thus, potentially increasing the diagnostic rate of these cases.

The analysis of the complete genome in the various projects of the NAGEN Program has shown, 1) the usefulness of these studies in the diagnosis and management of genetically based pathology, especially in rare diseases, and 2) a confirmation of the need to develop new bioinformatics tools that allow the analysis of the greatest number of genetic alterations possible to maximize their diagnostic yield. During the course of these NAGEN Program projects, different tools have been developed to allow the analysis of copy number variants (CNVs), short-tandem-repeats (STRs) and structural variants (SVs). However, one of the genetic alterations pending exploration is Uniparental Disomies (UPDs), where both copies of a chromosome or a region of these, are inherited from one parent only. There is no genetic material in these (regions of the) chromosomes from the other parent.

The project focuses on the optimization and validation of UPDhmm tool, a method based on a Markov Model to detect UPDs. UPDhmm considers 5 inheritance models: normal inheritance (Mendelian) and combinations of isodisomy/heterodisomy of maternal/paternal origin. Each

inheritance model defines the probability of finding each of the genotype combinations of the parents and the index case. Thus, we can define the most probable type of inheritance for each of the genomic positions, defining regions where it is very likely that there has been a UPD event.

Hypothesis: The optimization and technical validation of a bioinformatic tool that allows to discriminate the presence/absence of UPDs and to characterize the type of disomy, without the need to use multiple different tests, will allow to increase the diagnostic success in cases of rare diseases due to unusual inheritance patterns. The tool we propose improves the detection of uniparental disomies with respect to existing methods, increases precision and allows for a better characterization of the type of disomy.

1. Data description

Research data from the projects NAGEN1000 and NAGENpediatrics. Specifically, we use genomic data generated using whole genome sequencing analysis (Illumina, DRAGEN) from trios of the previously mentioned research projects. Such potential secondary use of the data was included in the informed consent signed by every participant of those projects. The corresponding ethical committee has approved this project (Comité de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos (CEIm, Navarra); Approval code: EC_2024/74 PS).

We re-use variant calling files (.vcf), generated using whole genome sequencing analysis, of:

- a. NAGEN1000 – 146 trios
- b. NAGENpediatrics – 222 trios / 8 quartets / 1 quintet

In total, we re-use for the analysis 1141 .vcf files of 377 different cases. These add up for a total of ~500GB of data. We estimate an additional 300GB storage for scripts and outcome files.

Activity	Data type	Legislation	Objective	From	Minimum time	Recommended time	Action at recommended time	Exceptions to elimination / cancelation / anonymization
Research	Genomic data	Ley de investigación biomédica (Spain) GDPR (EU) LOPDGDD (Spain)	Genetic analysis to detect uniparental disomies	Project onset; January 2025	End of the project; December 2026	End of the project; December 2026	Elimination	N/A – In case of need for medical purposes, the original copy may be recovered

2. Metadata and documentation accompanying the data.

- Cohort characterization - including cohort structure, demographics of the cases, inclusion and exclusion criteria, diagnosis status.
- Glossary – including file names and description.
- Description of the bioinformatic tool – including a GitHub repository linked to metadata in ZENODO.
- Description of HPC resources – including storage and hours of computational time.
- Data Management Plan – including different versions produced over the course of the project under an open license. Under CC BY 4.0 open license.

3. Data storage and back-up

Data is property of the Genomics Medicine Unit of Navarrabiomed.

This dataset is stored in NASERTIC, the Data Centre of Government of Navarra. This platform adheres to strict security measures and the genomic data is protected by multiple security layers. The Firewall displays a double layer from different suppliers. The security of the stored and newly generated data complies with the requirements of the National Security Scheme and the OCDE recommendations for risk management of digital security.

Data analyses is also performed in a computational cluster within NASERTIC. A specific Trusted Research Environment (TRE) will be created for the project.

Original genomic data is stored, backed up and managed in the same Data Centre, although independently from our data. A copy of the necessary files was transferred to our TRE, so there is no risk of permanently losing data. Thus, we do not plan to routinely backup data. The copy of the .vcf files will be deleted at the end of the project, while the generated data will be stored locally at the Genomics Medicine Unit of Navarrabiomed (leader of the project) (within a protected network managed and audited by the Government of Navarra).

4. Personal data processing

We use sensitive data. Genomic .vcf files can be used for re-identification of a person unequivocally. Therefore, personal data was dissociated from genomic files. The research team

only works with pseudonymised genomic data and phenotypic and/or demographic data is not required. We neither need to contact the patient. Thus, risk of reidentificación is minimised. Only Principal Investigators of NAGEN1000 (Dr Ángel Alonso Sánchez – Medical Genetics Service HUN) and NAGENpediatrics (Dra. Josune Hualde Olascoaga – Pediatrics Service HUN) safeguard decoding files. They are also the reference practitioners of the patients whose genomes were used. Therefore, results will be delivered only to these clinicians for them to consider the most appropriate clinical management.

Personal data treatment follows the requirements of the Reglamento General de Protección de datos (RGPD-Reglamento (UE) 2016/679, Ley Orgánica 3/2018) and the EHDS regulations.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

Raw genomic data will not be shared or deposited in a repository at any point since it is sensitive data. The results regarding the details and the performance of the tool and the clinical findings will be shared in a research article published in an indexed scientific journal under open licenses, always preserving personal data protection and personal identities. Prevalence of these disorders may be extremely low, so further permissions will be obtained if data shown in the publication may be enough to identify individuals.

Potentially, raw data may be accessible for re-use via NAGENdata platform upon request provided scientific and ethical approval be in place. Although this option is currently unavailable.

Code and specific information about the bioinformatic tool will be deposited in a repository (e.g. GitHub) and shared via a scientific publication.

Metadata will be deposited in an appropriate repository, such as ZENODO or similar, and linked to a persistent identifier. We will provide sufficient metadata to assure reusability and reproducibility of the tool, albeit input data will not be shared.

Personal data will not be transferred outside the institution.

6. Data management / FAIR

As mentioned above, NAGENdata will safeguard the original genomic and phenotypical data of all the participants included in this project. Any potential data discovery and access should be arrange via those responsible of that project. . In this platform, FAIR data objects include the data files, a persistent unique identifier and a description of the standards and formats used.